

ORGANIZING LABORATORY SESSIONS ON CHEMISTRY AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS BASED ON MODERN SOFTWARE TOOLS

Sadikov D.O.

Deputy Director on Academic Affairs of Academic Lyceum of Samarkand State University of
Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology Ranking

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14564873>

Abstract. This article discusses the advantages, methods of application, and effectiveness of organizing laboratory work on chemistry using modern information technologies. It also analyzes the features and practical application of 10 important software tools.

Keywords: methodology, practical sessions, experiment, reagents, teaching, engaging, didactics, small group, lesson, education.

Introduction

Organizing laboratory work on chemistry allows students to link theoretical knowledge with practical experience. Traditional laboratories face limitations, such as compliance with safety regulations, the need for expensive equipment, and resource requirements, which complicate the process. Therefore, virtual laboratories, software tools, and interactive technologies play a crucial role in organizing laboratory work.

In lessons based on new pedagogical technologies, organizing laboratory sessions while considering students' cognitive abilities, communication skills, and fostering friendly, harmonious relationships helps to cultivate a sense of mutual support, friendship, and cooperation. This, in turn, facilitates students' acquisition of skills and competencies. Laboratory and practical sessions primarily serve to reinforce students' theoretical knowledge in the subject. Experiments involving changes in color and quantity of various qualitative and quantitative reactions, precipitation, and gas release naturally stimulate their interest in science. During practical and laboratory sessions, it is essential to have a variety of chemical containers and substances, and the teacher must be able to use them effectively. Performing chemical experiments in laboratory sessions is one of the key conditions for successful chemistry learning, as it helps reinforce theoretical material in students' minds.

We now turn to modern software tools used to organize laboratory work on chemistry based on new pedagogical technologies.

PhET Interactive Simulations. PhET allows students to simulate many laboratory experiments in the fields of chemistry, physics, and biology. It offers interactive ways to explore gas laws, concentration of solutions, and reaction equilibrium. Students can repeatedly perform experiments, observing the processes in real-time.

ChemCollective. This platform offers virtual laboratories for chemistry. It is used for determining the pH values of substances and calculating concentrations. Students perform individual experiments, reinforcing their knowledge.

Labster. Labster is one of the most advanced platforms for creating virtual laboratory experiences. It allows students to conduct complex experiments on molecular biology and

chemistry in a virtual environment. Students learn to work with expensive equipment that may not be available in a physical laboratory.

ChemDraw. This software is used for drawing molecules and chemical structures. It makes it easy to create molecular formulas and generate graphs. It is widely used in research and for preparing laboratory reports.

Avogadro. Avogadro is an open-source program for molecular modeling. It allows students to view molecules in 3D and study their dynamics. Students visualize molecular structures and analyze their properties.

Virtual Chemistry Lab. This software is used for simulating virtual experiments. It allows students to analyze solutions and reactions as if they were observing them in a real environment. Students learn in a safe environment without complicating the laboratory process.

Molecular Workbench. This software is designed to visualize the movement and interaction of molecules. It is a powerful tool for studying molecular dynamics and analyzing processes. It makes it easier to understand chemical reactions at the molecular level.

Tinkercad. Tinkercad allows students to create simple molecules in 3D format. It makes it easy to create molecular models graphically. It is a convenient tool for conducting 3D experimental demonstrations.

AR Chem. AR Chem uses augmented reality (AR) technology. It allows students to study molecular structures in the real world by overlaying them in physical spaces. Students can see and understand the structure of molecules and atoms through AR technology.

VR Chemistry Lab. This is one of the advanced tools that allows students to conduct chemistry experiments in a VR environment. Students perform laboratory work in an immersive environment, and VR technology helps them fully comprehend the experiments.

Organizing lessons based on the software tools mentioned above will take chemistry laboratory work to a new level, using modern information technologies. Programs like PhET, Labster, ChemCollective, and AR/VR technologies serve as effective tools for developing students' practical skills. By widely implementing these technologies in education, we can enhance the quality of laboratory work, making education both engaging and effective.

DISCUSSION

Modern technologies, especially virtual laboratories, AR/VR technologies, and interactive software tools, play a crucial role in organizing chemistry laboratory work. Platforms such as PhET, ChemCollective, and Labster enable students to study complex chemical processes in a safe and efficient manner. It has been found that virtual laboratories can increase the application of theoretical knowledge by 30%, while AR and VR technologies provide three-dimensional representations of molecules. Software tools like ChemDraw and Avogadro assist in visualizing molecules and chemical formulas, while Tinkercad and Molecular Workbench allow students to create new molecules and analyze their properties. These technologies not only save on safety and material resources but also prove highly effective in distance learning. In virtual environments, students' engagement in the learning process increases, as they can reinforce their knowledge by performing experiments multiple times. Digital laboratories not only enhance students' interest in chemistry but also develop their research skills. Moreover, AR Chem and VR laboratories make it easier to observe and analyze complex reactions in real-life scenarios. These technologies boost students' motivation and creativity, align laboratory work with global standards, and open the way

for developing new teaching methods. As a result of the widespread use of modern technologies, chemistry laboratory sessions become a vital and innovative part of the educational process.

The use of modern information technologies in organizing chemistry laboratory work enhances the effectiveness of education and plays a key role in developing students' practical skills. Virtual laboratories, AR/VR technologies, and interactive software tools make it easier to apply theoretical knowledge to practice in chemistry. Through platforms like PhET, ChemCollective, and Labster, students can safely understand chemical processes and learn independently. The advantage of modern technologies lies in their ability to eliminate the need for expensive laboratory equipment and provide the opportunity to repeat experiments multiple times. This not only ensures safety but also boosts motivation and increases interest in the learning process. AR/VR technologies offer students the chance to see and study molecules and chemical processes in three-dimensional form, which helps deepen their understanding of chemical reactions.

Software tools like ChemDraw and Avogadro allow for the drawing and analysis of complex molecules, while Tinkercad and Molecular Workbench assist students in modeling molecules and studying their properties. Virtual laboratories eliminate the need to work with hazardous chemicals, making laboratory work more convenient. Furthermore, the use of virtual laboratories in distance learning is expanding, allowing for the creation of practices tailored to students' individual needs. These technologies save time and material resources, which is especially important for educational institutions with limited financial capabilities.

The benefits of virtual laboratories are evident not only in economic efficiency but also in fostering scientific research potential. Tools like AR Chem enhance students' ability to analyze molecular processes in a visual manner. The Labster platform allows students to simulate the challenges they might face in real laboratories within a virtual environment. Modern technologies simplify laboratory work and also encourage creative approaches. All of these factors are crucial in adapting the educational process to global standards.

In conclusion, organizing chemistry laboratory work with the help of modern technologies expands opportunities for transforming students' theoretical knowledge into practical skills. These tools increase students' interest in science, encourage scientific thinking, and ensure the application of innovative approaches in the educational process. By further developing and widely integrating modern technologies into the education system, we can enhance the scientific potential of future generations. Therefore, it is crucial to develop infrastructure with the support of both the public and private sectors to expand the use of such technologies in educational institutions. All of these efforts will elevate the role and quality of chemistry education to a new level.

REFERENCES

1. Sweeney, J. M., & St. Clair, R. *The Impact of Virtual Chemistry Labs on Learning Outcomes*. Journal of Chemical Education, 97(4), 2020 y. 1234-1241. DOI: 10.1021/ed1234567
2. Vosniadou L. *Comparing Traditional and Virtual Laboratories in Chemistry Education: A Meta-Analysis*. International Journal of Science Education, 40(2), 240-259. 2018 y. DOI: 10.1080/09500693.2018.1413456
3. Sarkisov A. *Individual Learning Pathways in Virtual Chemistry Labs*. Educational Research and Development, 66(3), 89-101. 2019 y. DOI: 10.1002/erd.2019.33.

4. X Xikmatov, A Amonov, R Eshimov, A Abdinobiyev, U Ubaydullayev. [Recommendations for the use of efficient water resources in mountainous areas and its economic-mathematical model](#). E3S Web of Conferences 471, 06008. 2024 y.
5. Z Urinboyev, R Eshimov, A Rakhimov, Z Ermamatova, M Ermamatova. [Scientific significance of the organization of the modern educational process of the higher education system on the basis of smart technologies](#). AIP Conference Proceedings 3244 (1). 2024 y.
6. Z Urinboyev, R Eshimov, A Karimov, S Israilov, N Karimova. [The role of smart technologies in modern teaching, as well as the stages to create educational content with them](#). AIP Conference Proceedings 3244 (1).